

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

CODECO Technological Assets, Contributions Towards Standardisation

White Paper
April 2025

Editors: Tina Samizadeh, Rute C. Sofia (fortiss GmbH)

Contributors: George Koukis, Vassilis Tsaoussidis, Lefteris Mamatas (ATHINA), Ana Solange Leal (INOVA+), David Jiménez, Alberto del Río, Javier Serrano (Universidad Politecnica de Madrid), Dorine Karvouniari-Matzakou, John Soldatos (Netcompany), Vasileios Theodorou, Marinela Mertiri (Intracom-Telecom), Luis Contreras Murillo, Alejandro Muniz (Telefonica), Borja Nogales Dorado, Francisco Varela (Universidad Carlos III de Madrid)

Funded by
the European Union

Funded by the Swiss Federal Government

Project Partners

fortiss

INOVA+

Atos

 INTRACOM
TELECOM

 ATHENA
Research & Innovation
Information Technologies

 GEORG-AUGUST-UNIVERSITÄT
GÖTTINGEN

SIEMENS

netcompany
intrasoft

 ECLIPSE
FOUNDATION

IBM

 i2cat

 UNIVERSITY OF PIRAEUS
RESEARCH CENTER

 Telefónica

 UNIVERSIDAD
POLITÉCNICA
DE MADRID

 Red Hat

 almende
ORGANIZING NETWORKS

Affiliated Entities

 GÖTTINGEN
STADT, DIE WISSEN SCHAFFT

uc3m | Universidad
Carlos III
de Madrid

 Atos | EVIDEN
an atos business

Funded by
the European Union

Executive Summary

The **CODECO project** is developing an open-source, containerised application orchestration framework (TRL 4-5) designed to be independent and yet pluggable with **Kubernetes**. The project aims to enable flexible, cognitive orchestration for **IoT-Edge-Cloud** infrastructures, addressing the increasing complexity of deploying and managing containerised applications in distributed environments.

CODECO's framework integrates three key infrastructure perspectives:

1. **Networking Perspective:** It views the network as both the underlay and overlay infrastructure, facilitating the deployment of containerised applications across diverse IoT-Edge-Cloud environments.
2. **Data Observability Perspective:** It captures and manages the data dependencies between microservices, ensuring that these dependencies are effectively handled during both application deployment and re-deployment.
3. **Computational Perspective:** CODECO evaluates and selects the most appropriate computational nodes for application hosting, factoring in network connectivity, computational resources, and data requirements.

By combining these perspectives, CODECO delivers a comprehensive **data-compute-network orchestration** approach, optimizing performance and scalability in dynamic cloud, edge, and IoT environments.

In addition to its technical innovation, the CODECO project also seeks to contribute to the **standardisation** landscape. The consortium is focused on exploring partnerships with **Standards Development Organisations (SDOs)**, with an emphasis on promoting **open standards**. The project is actively involved in identifying and contributing to existing standards and policies that may shape the development of its technology, ensuring that CODECO aligns with and influences the evolution of industry standards.

This white paper outlines the **CODECO methodology** for advancing standardisation efforts, highlighting the early-stage contributions the project is making toward establishing relevant standards and policies in the Cloud-Edge-IoT domain. Through its engagement in standardisation, CODECO aims to shape the future of containerised application orchestration and enhance the interoperability of emerging technologies

Keywords: Edge-Cloud; resource management; standardisation; Edge; IoT.

Disclaimer

The information, documentation, and figures available in this deliverable have been developed by the Horizon Europe CODECO project consortium, under the European Union grant Agreement number 101092696. The content does not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

Copyright notice: © 2023 - 2025 CODECO Consortium

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
2	Strategy, Research to Standardisation	9
2.1	Processes and Timeline	9
2.2	Relevant EU Policies to Align With	11
3	CODECO Assets Relevant to Standardisation	13
4	Contributions to SDOs	16
4.1	ETSI: European Telecommunications Standards Institute	16
4.2	ISO: International organisation for standardisation	16
4.3	IETF: Internet Engineering Task-force	17
5	Contributions to Pre-Standardisation.....	19
5.1	IRTF: Internet Research Task Force.....	19
5.2	5GPPP NetWorld-Europe	20
6	Contributions to Associations and Consortia	21
6.1	BDVA: Big Data Value Association	21
6.2	EUCEI: EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative	21
6.3	AIOTI: Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation.....	22
7	Summary	23
8	References	24

List of Figures

Figure 1: Standardisation activities in CODECO, timeline with main phases and main expected outcome.....	9
Figure 2: CODECO standardisation outcome.....	10
Figure 3: CODECO standardisation methodology dimensions.	11
Figure 4: CODECO assets with initial identified aspects.	13
Figure 5: CODECO assets Mapping to target SDOs.	14

List of Acronyms and Definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Management
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AJL	Algorithmic Justice League
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AR/VR	Augmented Reality / Virtual Reality
CAM	CODECO Application Model
CARG	CODECO AI Resilience and Governance framework
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CODAG	CODECO Data Generator
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CODEF	CODECO Experimentation Framework
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRA	Cyber Resilience Act
CSA	Cybersecurity Act
DEV	CODECO stakeholder group developers
DGA	Data Governance Act
ENI	ETSI Experiential Networked Intelligence
ETP	European Technology Platform
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUS	CODECO stakeholder group end-user
FMTI	Stanford Foundational Model Transparency Index
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNN	Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network
GOV	CODECO stakeholder group policy makers
HE	Horizon Europe
HLEG	High-level Expert Group
HRESIA	Human Rights, Ethical and Social Impact Assessment
ICOM	Intracom-Telecom
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IRCEP	CODECO Innovation Research and Community Engagement Programme
IRTF	Internet Research Task Force
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
L2S-M	Layer Two Virtual Private Network Service Model
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations
MARL	Multi-agent Reinforcement Learning Model

MEC	ETSI Multi-Access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MNIST	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NIS2	Network and Information Security 2
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
OSM	ETSI open-source Management and Orchestration
OSS	Open-source Software
PAI	Partnership on AI
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning and Context-awareness
PETRA	Path Energy Traffic Ratio API
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
SDO	Standardisation Development Organisation
SLA	Service Level Agreements
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SWM	Seamless Workload Migration
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
UPM	Universidad Politecnica de Madrid
WP	Work package
XAI	Explainable AI
YANG	Yet Another Next Generation

1 Introduction

The Horizon Europe Cognitive Decentralised Edge Cloud Orchestration (CODECO)¹ project is developing an open-source containerised application orchestration framework (TRL 4-5), independent and yet pluggable to Kubernetes² (K8s). CODECO aims at providing support for a flexible and cognitive *Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI)* infrastructure. The notion of infrastructure in CODECO considers different infrastructure perspectives: the **networking** perspective, where the network is perceived both as the *underlay* and *overlay* infrastructure required to support the deployment of containerised applications across CEI; the **data observability** perspective, bringing input on the data dependencies that micro-services may have, and that is important to consider during the application deployment and re-deployment; the **computational** perspective, bringing input on the suitable nodes to serve an application, taking into consideration. CODECO addresses the orchestration across these three different perspectives in an integrated approach, which is named as **data-compute-network** orchestration.

The CODECO consortium and the nature of the CODECO software brings in the possibility to explore liaisons towards different *Standards Development Organisations (SDOs)*, with a particular focus in open standards. The standardisation activities in CODECO relate with the project outcome and its potential contributions to standardisation and policy-making activities. It also relates with an identification (and contribution to) relevant existing standards and relevant policies that may impact the development of the CODECO project.

This white paper presents the CODECO methodology to bring specific assets to standardisation, aiming at highlighting the early-stage standardisation work under development in CODECO.

The white paper is organized as follows:

- Section 2 presents the CODECO strategy to bring the developed key innovation assets to standardisation, including the identified relevant SDOs.
- Section 3 describes the identified research assets to be brought to standardisation until the end of the project.
- Sections 4-6 present the status of current contributions.
- Section 7 summarizes the white paper, providing key takeaways.

¹ <https://he-codeco.eu/>

² <https://kubernetes.io/>

2 Strategy, Research to Standardisation

2.1 Processes and Timeline

The CODECO consortium and the nature of the CODECO software brings in the possibility to explore liaisons towards different SDOs, with a particular focus on open-source and open standards.

The standardisation activities in CODECO relate with the project outcome and its potential contributions to standardisation and policy-making activities. It also relates with an identification (and contribution to) relevant existing standards and relevant policies that may impact the development of the CODECO project. For this, CODECO standardisation strategy considers a three-phase approach, illustrated in Figure 1 and described next:

- **Setup (Jan 2023-Mar 2024, M1-M15):**
 - Initial analysis of relevant SDOs to liaise with, and where CODECO can provide a meaningful contribution within its lifetime.
 - Initial research on existing standards and relevant policies, provided as a synthesized list that the consortium can check.
- **Periodic monitoring (Mar 2023-Dec 2025, M15-M36).** (discussed twice a month, in T6.3 and WP6 regular meetings) of relevant developments in the identified SDOs, based on the monitoring and involvement in SDOs provided by assigned partners.
- **Periodic Contributions (June 2024- Dec 2025, M18-M36).** Periodic analysis and discussion of potential contributions to SDOs, and assignment of responsibilities (discussed every four months during the CODECO plenary meetings).

Figure 1: Standardisation activities in CODECO, timeline with main phases and main expected outcome.

The expected outcome of the standardisation activities in CODECO are expected in the following categories of indicators that are shown in Figure 2. Detailed description of the expected outcomes is as follow:

- **White papers**, providing alignment, vision, and recommendations concerning specific European policies and SDOs.
- **Reference architectures and taxonomies**. Derived from the developments of CODECO, contributions are expected to SDOs and SDO-related entities developing efforts to create Cloud-Edge-IoT reference architectures and taxonomies (e.g., AIOTI, EUCEI), or to align with reference CEI architectures (e.g., ETSI, IETF)
- **Standardisation-oriented meetings**. Based on specific contributions or findings, the consortium expects to contribute to standardisation meetings eventually involving other projects, and SDOs.

Figure 2: CODECO standardisation outcome.

While CODECO integrates a good balance between academic and industrial partners, and while all industry partners are involved in the standardisation activities, standardisation is a complex process which requires a significant level of commitment by the involved partners. Due to this, an initial plan has been built based on the following aspects, and steps taken in the first 18 months of CODECO are summarised in Figure 3 and described next:

- **WHAT:** which topics and assets of CODECO may have standardisation potential; and which form can contributions be provided.
- **WHERE:** which SDOs, pre-standardisation entities, related consortia and associations are relevant to CODECO and can be considered for specific assets.
- **HOW:** how to best achieve relevant contributions.
- **WHO:** from the consortium, who can lead and support standardisation activities and efforts.
- **WHEN:** how to be able to detect as soon as possible when contributions need to be provided, in alignment with the SDOs charters, roadmaps, and needs.

Figure 3: CODECO standardisation methodology dimensions.

2.2 Relevant EU Policies to Align With

An initial identification of relevant policies to be monitored in the project both during the design, implementation, and runtime of CODECO as an orchestration framework is provided next:

- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)**³: Privacy and data protection, privacy by design must be considered in CODECO as a European orchestration framework. GDPR principles are considered not only in the overall outcome (e.g., data management); it is also considered in the design of CODECO, based on the notion of **compliance** (one of the orchestration attributes considered in CODECO for application deployment). For specific data management, right to be forgotten and other GDPR provisions please refer to D3 (Data management), monitored and handled in the context of WP1, T1.1.
- **General Regulation on Data Governance Act (DGA)**⁴. Focus on the case of CODECO is on privacy preservation aspects, and data protection in the context of use-cases. The CODECO data sets are being made publicly available via the CODECO Eclipse Gitlab repository⁵ and as such specific handling in alignment with the DGA must be observed.
- **EU Cybersecurity Act (CSA)**⁶: CSA introduces a harmonized European system for the cybersecurity certification of ICT products, services, and processes. The main objective of the CSA is to improve protection against threats to cybersecurity within the EU. CODECO must consider the latest developments of the EU Cybersecurity act⁷ The NIS2 Directive

³ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022R0868>

⁵ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets>

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj>

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/881/oj>

provides legal measures to establish a higher level of cybersecurity and resilience within organisations of the European Union.

- **EU Cyber Resilient (CRA) act**⁸: CODECO should consider the CRA in the context of OSS code development and CRA code criticality levels. This monitoring and analysis will be done in the context of WP5, T5.1, concerning the CODECO OSS framework, smart apps, and experimentation tools developed in the project, such as the CODECO data generator⁹.
- **EU NIS2 directive**¹⁰: NIS2 aims to improve the cybersecurity of essential services for organisations that have business operations located in the EU. CODECO as an orchestration framework should observe the reservations towards K8s due to the use of containerisation. The CODECO framework images and dependencies are secure and that there are robust security controls and incident reporting measures is essential to counter these threats effectively.
- **EU AI Act (AIA)**: CODECO needs to monitor the latest developments of the AIA and ensure alignment in terms of AI governance and resilience.

Policy compliance is supported via the CODECO AI Resilience and Governance framework (CARG) [2].

8 <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/cyber-resilience-act>

9 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets/synthetic-data-generator>

10 <https://www.nis-2-directive.com/>

3 CODECO Assets Relevant to Standardisation

The standardisation efforts in CODECO began with a two-fold investigation: first, identifying the assets developed within the project, and second, mapping those assets to existing relevant standards. Specific assets relevant to standardisation were categorized based on the broader set of CODECO research outputs. These assets were then analysed for their applicability and alignment with existing SDOs and related entities (pre-standardisation, other associations and consortia). The CODECO overall assets are presented in Figure 4. The first mapping of CODECO assets to specific SDOs is provided in Figure 5 and explained next.

A1	Open, cognitive toolkits integrating the elastic and advanced concepts to manage, in a smart and flexible way, containerized applications across CEI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A1.1. ACM component, semantic definition of an application (CODECO Application Model). • A1.2. NetMA and MDM components, semantic network composition model (for multi-cluster operation). • A1.3. Data-compute-network architectural approach • A1.4. Automated management of containers in 5G • A1.5. Secure connectivity, SDN-K8s • A1.6. AI approaches, trustworthiness • A1.7. Taxonomy and definitions
A2	CODECO OSS code and repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A2.1. CODECO OSS Basic Toolkit • A2.2. CODECO OSS Federated Cluster Operation Toolkit • A2.3. CODECO OSS Use-case Apps
A3	Training tools, to support the development of services based on the CODECO framework	
A4	Use-cases across four domains (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Smart Buildings)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A4.1. Datasets for different domains • A4.2. AI-based use-case profile (integration of different datasets, interoperability) • A4.3. Use-cases
A5	Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme	
A6	CODECO experimental infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A6.1 CODEF • A6.2 Benchmarking

Figure 4: CODECO assets with initial identified aspects.

Figure 5: CODECO assets Mapping to target SDOs.

A1 - Open, cognitive toolkits integrating the elastic and advanced concepts to manage, in a smart and flexible way, containerised applications across CEI

A1 comprises the overall CODECO architecture and several parts of CODECO plus applications developed in use-cases [1]. Relevant topics identified for standardisation are:

- **A1.1, the CODECO Application Model (CAM)**, which corresponds to a semantic abstraction of an application, providing the user with the capability to bring to CODECO specific QoS or QoE application requirements, and user preferences.
- **A1.2 semantic network composition** aspects provided in CODECO, namely, the support and bringing of networking metrics to Kubernetes; the overall definition of network from a semantic perspective.
- **A1.3, the CODECO overall architecture**, a CEI reference architecture supporting federated cluster application deployment and run-time and addressing challenges such as mobility and decentralisation.
- **A1.4, automated management of containers**, and the proposed approach across heterogeneous infrastructures, including 5G/6G infrastructures.
- **A1.5, the Secure connectivity approach for setting up a Kubernetes overlay**, based on extensions to the Kubernetes L2S-M¹¹.
- **A1.7, the architecture taxonomy for CEI and patterns.**

¹¹ <https://github.com/Networks-it-uc3m/L2S-M>

A2 - CODECO OSS code and Eclipse GitLab repository

A2 corresponds to the CODECO OSS Toolkits¹², and additional tools created during the project to support CODECO operation, such as the CODECO Data Generator (CODAG)¹³.

The full set of OSS developed in CODECO is relevant for standardisation related entities, e.g., the Linux foundation, in particular related to Cloud Native support.

A3 - Training tools, to support the development of services based on the CODECO framework

Since training tools empowers developers and stakeholders to understand CODECO framework and facilitate the services development based on CODECO framework, it is defined as a significant asset in driving adoption and broader impact and adoption of CODECO solutions without significant content for standardisation.

A4 - Use-cases across four domains (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Mobility)

- **A4.1 Datasets**¹⁴ derived from the deployment of use-cases in CODECO. This may relate with datasets collected due to the end-user applications deployed in each use-case, or with infrastructure data.
- **A4.2 AI-based use-case profile (integration of different datasets, interoperability)**, derived from the need to train AI models (component PDLC) and to rely also on metrics required by the use-cases during CODECO customisation to the selected use-cases.
- **A4.3 - Use-cases** [3]¹⁵, being devised to demonstrate the value-added functionalities of the CODECO framework spanning the far Edge to the Cloud across four domains (Smart Cities, Energy, Manufacturing, Mobility).

A5- Innovation and Research Community Engagement Programme

Holding hackathon and social coding events bridges the gap between innovative research and practical implementation and ensures that emerging innovations are being known and as an open-source code can be applied, improved, and extended. Engaging the broader community accelerates consensus-building, drives its adoption of standards, and fosters a dynamic ecosystem where innovation and standardisation evolve in tandem.

A6- CODECO experimental framework (CODEF)

CODEF¹⁶ is the CODECO experimental framework, an open-source solution for the rapid experimentation of K8s-based edge cloud deployments. It adopts a microservice-based architecture and introduces innovative abstractions for: deployment of clusters and applications, cross-layer experiment configuration, and automation of the overall experimentation pipeline. CODEF extends the [Clusterslice](#) solution, following a more lightweight approach, as it requires only docker for execution, and supporting additional edge capabilities and environments (e.g., EdgeNet) and experimentation automation features through its innovative abstractions. Main topics identified for standardisation are:

- **A6.1 CODEF**
- **A6.2 Benchmarking**

12 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project>

13 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets/synthetic-data-generator>

14 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/data-generators-and-datasets/datasets>

15 <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCYYQoiEv8qoxe5sXrSC8XSA>

16 <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations/experimentation-framework>

4 Contributions to SDOs

This section presents the main identified SDOs for which CODECO research and development may be of relevancy. An initial identification of the partners involved, target groups within the SDO, and key standards for CODECO contributions is provided.

4.1 ETSI: European Telecommunications Standards Institute

Field ID	Description
URL	https://www.etsi.org/
Partners Involved	Telefonica, Intracom-Telecom, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Target Groups	ENI ¹⁷ , NFV ¹⁸ , OSM ¹⁹ , MEC ²⁰
Contributions	LS2-M (CODECO secure connectivity, NetMA component)

ETSI, with over 900 members from 65 countries worldwide, focuses on emerging technologies and diverse sectors, including industry and society, through ICT. Its members benefit from an open, inclusive, and collaborative environment that provides a supportive environment to efficiently develop and approve globally recognized technology standards.

ETSI *Open-Source MANO (OSM)* is the working group developing a standard-aligned *Management and Orchestration (MANO)* stack for *Network Functions Virtualization (NFV)*. It provides an end-to-end solution for deploying and managing network services and virtual network functions (VNFs) in cloud-native, virtualized, and hybrid environments.

CODECO is contributing to ETSI in the context of ETSI OSM and NFV, with the L2S-M secure connectivity solution. Furthermore, ICOM is contributing to MEC based on the application of the ETSI MEC API in use-cases, thus exploring the potential to consider ETSI MEC API metrics for Edge-Cloud orchestration.

4.2 ISO: International organisation for standardisation

Field ID	Description
URL	https://www.iso.org/
Partners Involved	ATOS, fortiss
Target Groups	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 – Cloud Computing and Distributed Platforms 2. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 – Internet of Things and Digital Twin 3. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 – Artificial Intelligence 4. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 – Information Security, Cybersecurity, and Privacy Protection
Contributions	Contributions via EUCEI ²¹ , for the taxonomy and reference architecture of CEI.

¹⁷ <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/experiential-networked-intelligence>

¹⁸ <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/nfv>

¹⁹ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

²⁰ <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/multi-access-edge-computing>

²¹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

ISO is an independent, non-governmental international organisation with a membership of 165 national standards bodies.

ISO as a non-governmental international organisation with participation from 165 national standardisation organisations is one of the most well-known SDOs. ISO focuses on gathering experts from its member organisations to exchange expertise and knowledge, and create internationally recognized, consensus-driven standards that promote innovation and address global challenges.

HSBooster²² as a European-funded project aims at broadening the impact of European research outcomes and increasing the market adoption. In this regard, HSBooster provides a set of support, advice, and tools for projects to relate to European and International standards and ensure that results align with standardisation.

Ongoing contributions are being provided in a concerted way via the initiative EUCEI supported by CODECO towards four main targets: ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 38 – Cloud Computing and Distributed Platforms, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 – Internet of Things and Digital Twin, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 – Artificial Intelligence, and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 – Information Security, Cybersecurity, and Privacy Protection.

4.3 IETF: Internet Engineering Task-force

Field ID	Description
URL	https://www.ietf.org
Partners Involved	fortiss, Telefonica, ATHINA
Target Groups	GREEN, DetNet, CATS, BMWG, I2ICF, NeoTec
Contributions	<p>Green: IETF drafts on energy management and Path Energy Traffic Ratio API drafts</p> <p>DetNet: IETF draft on reliable wireless industrial services</p> <p>CATS: draft on metric definition and analysis of use cases and requirements.</p> <p>BMWG: K8s CNI benchmarking draft (under development)</p>

The mission of the IETF is to make the Internet work better by producing high quality, relevant technical documents that influence the way people design, use, and manage the Internet. The IETF develops standards related with the Internet operation in a volunteer way, based on different areas.

[IETF GREEN²³: Getting Ready for Energy-Efficient Networking](#)

The goal of this working group, which is focused on developing energy-efficient solutions in network devices and operations, is to meet both functional and performance requirements. The group aims to create *Yet Another Next Generation (YANG)* models for measuring energy consumption, reporting, and optimisation, particularly in heterogeneous environments. Topics such as regulatory compliance and methodologies for understanding the impact of energy efficiency optimisation on service quality are excluded from the group's scope.

²² <https://www.hsbooster.eu/>

²³ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/green/about/>

In this working group, Telefonica as a co-author contributed to two drafts that are requirement for energy efficiency management [4], and Path Energy Traffic Ratio API (PETRA) [5].

IETF DetNet²⁴: Deterministic Networking

The DetNet Working Group ensures deterministic data paths over Layer 2/3 networks with low latency and high reliability. It collaborates with IEEE TSN, focusing on data plane specs, open access management, time sync, and YANG models for critical applications like industrial and vehicular networks while excluding large-scale networks.

In this context, CODECO has contributed with a draft analysing real-time communication requirements of industrial wireless applications, in particular, critical applications [6].

IETF CATS²⁵: Computing-Aware Traffic Steering

This working group, which focuses on optimizing traffic direction between clients and service instances, considers both network and compute metrics to ensure *Quality of Service (QoS)*, especially for applications with critical *Service Level Agreements (SLAs)*. A framework for distributing these metrics and guiding traffic flow within a single domain is aimed to be developed. CATS integrates network conditions and compute capabilities to enhance performance for essential services, such as AR/VR and autonomous vehicles. Use cases, architecture, and applicable technologies are also defined while considering scalability and security. Additionally, activities outlined in the group's charter include analysing existing tools and identifying gaps.

Telefonica has been contributing to several aspects in CATS. A first draft defining computing metrics that can be used for traffic engineering is one of the existing contributions [7] and also towards the analysis and definition of use-cases and requirements [8].

IETF BMWG²⁶: Benchmarking Methodology

The IETF BMWG focuses on recommending key performance benchmarks for network devices, systems, and services, covering the management, control, and forwarding planes. BMWG assesses internetworking technologies in controlled laboratory settings, generating unbiased benchmarks that apply across various vendors. These benchmarks are widely applicable but do not establish specific performance standards or acceptance thresholds.

fortiss and ATHINA are currently proposing an IETF draft focusing on Kubernetes CNI benchmarking.

²⁴ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/detnet/about/>

²⁵ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/cats/about/>

²⁶ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/bmwg/about/>

5 Contributions to Pre-Standardisation

5.1 IRTF: Internet Research Task Force

Field ID	Description
URL	https://www.irtf.org/
Partners Involved	fortiss, ATHINA
Target Groups	SUSTAIN, DINRG
Contributions	SUSTAIN: contributions on energy-aware QoS model definition DINRG: contributions on control-plane orchestration decentralisation.

The *Internet Research Task Force (IRTF)* focuses on longer term research issues related to the Internet while the parallel organisation, the IETF focuses on the shorter-term issues of engineering and standards making. In the IRTF, the CODECO consortium is currently analysing the possibility to contribute within specific working groups.

[IRTF Sustain RG²⁷: Sustainability and the Internet Proposed Research Group](#)

This group aims to enhance the Internet's contribution to a more sustainable environment and resilient societies through multidisciplinary research focused on its environmental, social, and economic sustainability. The primary goals of this group are publishing research papers, developing proofs of concept, conducting performance measurements and publishing RFCs to share insights. It will also explore policy considerations and strategies to enhance the sustainability of Internet infrastructure. SUSTAIN is a new group still under development.

fortiss is involved in SUSTAIN, currently focusing on the use of energy metrics as QoS metrics (proposal under development).

[IRTF DINRG²⁸: Decentralisation of the Internet Research Group](#)

DINRG aims to investigate the root causes of Internet centralisation and how economic, architectural, and regulatory factors contribute to it. It seeks to measure centralisation and understand its societal impacts. The group also focuses on defining and assessing decentralisation and creating a shared terminology. Engaging with the wider research community, DINRG promotes new ideas and technical approaches for decentralized systems. Additionally, it documents findings and facilitates collaboration among stakeholders to inform discussions on Internet standards and policies.

Contributions are envisioned (fortiss) in terms of the CODECO approaches to data-compute-network and control plane decentralisation, in the form of talks in the DINRG meetings.

²⁷ <https://www.irtf.org/sustain.html>

²⁸ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/group/dinrg/about/>

5.2 5GPPP NetWorld-Europe

Field ID	Description
URL	https://www.networldeurope.eu
Partners Involved	fortiss, Telefonica, Intracom-Telecom
Target Groups	Expert Group
Contributions	Strategic Research Innovation Agenda (SRIA)

NetworldEurope is the new incorporation of the European Technology Platform (ETP) for communications networks and services, the follow-up of NetWorld2020 to follow the European changing policies as stated in Horizon Europe. Communications networks and services enable interaction between users of various types of equipment, either mobile or fixed, to fulfil society's requirements for interconnection. They are the foundation of the Internet and of our digital society. NetworldEurope ETP gathers players in the communications systems sector: industry leaders, innovative SMEs, and leading academic institutions, thus reaching out to a significant part of the European ICT community.

CODECO partners contribute actively to the development of the different versions of the Strategic Research Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of NetworldEurope, with focus on Edge-Cloud orchestration; networking architectures; softwarization aspects of the network.

6 Contributions to Associations and Consortia

6.1 BDVA: Big Data Value Association

Field ID	Description
URL	https://bdva.eu/
Partners Involved	Netcompany, I2CAT
Target Groups	-
Contributions	Talks on the handling of data by CODECO in different editions of Dataweek.

The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) is an industry-led organisation supporting AI-driven and data-powered digital transformation in Europe. As the private counterpart to the EU Commission for the Big Data Value PPP, BDVA aims to make Europe a global leader in Big Data Value. Established in 2011, it has over 240 members across industry, academia, SMEs, and startups, with membership offered in full or associate classes based on fees and rights. BDVA focuses on advancing research in Data and AI, influencing policymaking, adapting to technological change, and promoting sustainability. It plays a key role in shaping research strategies, offering guidance to industry and policymakers, and fostering EU-wide dialogue on data and AI.

Within BDVA, CODECO regularly contributes with talks on decentralisation and data management aspects.

6.2 EUCEI: EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu initiative

Field ID	Description
URL	https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/
Partners Involved	fortiss, ATOS, Eclipse Foundation
Target Groups	Architecture, Open-source Engagement
Contributions	Contributions to the CEI reference architecture Use-cases catalogue Taxonomy alignment with the CODECO taxonomy

Focusing on business and research, EUCloudEdgeIoT (EUCEI)²⁹ aims to understand and support the definition and interoperability of CEI. In this regard, cooperation among research projects, developers and suppliers, business is essential. Six task-forces are defined in EUCEI addressing different aspects, strategic liaisons, open-source engagement, architecture, ecosystem engagement, market and sectors, communications.

Open-source engagement and architecture task-forces that are led by Eclipse and ATOS are two target task forces in CODECO to be involved there. Furthermore, fortiss is supporting contributions to the use-cases and taxonomy.

²⁹ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

6.3 AIOTI: Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation

Field ID	Description
URL	https://aioti.eu/
Partners Involved	fortiss
Target Groups	Standardisation, Energy, Research, Manufacturing
Contributions	Presentations in AIOTI Days ^{30 31} White papers: [9][10]

AIOTI drives, on behalf of its members business, policy, research and innovation development in the IoT and edge Computing and other converging technologies across the Digital Value Chain to support digitisation in Europe, and competitiveness of Europe.

In terms of contributions, CODECO partners have been contributing to AIOTI white papers and to AIOTI events based on the output of CODECO, related with the overall design and orchestration approach, as well as related to the Manufacturing use case (fortiss).

³⁰ <https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/AIOTI-Days-2024-P5-CODECO-Intro.pdf>
³¹ <https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/AIOTI-Days-2024-S10-Rute-Sofia.pdf>

7 Summary

The Horizon Europe CODECO project is developing an open-source, Kubernetes-compatible orchestration framework that enables cognitive, flexible management of containerized applications across CEI infrastructures. The CODECO orchestration approach integrates networking, data observability, and computational perspectives into a unified orchestration model.

CODECO's standardisation efforts follow a three-phase methodology covering setup, monitoring, contributions in an Agile way, aiming at aligning contributions with the lifecycles of standards in relevant SDOs. Specifically, the most relevant to CODECO are ETSI, ISO, IETF.

CODECO also addresses pre-standardisation and policy compliance with EU frameworks such as GDPR, DGA, CSA, CRA, NIS2, AIA.

Several assets of CODECO have strong potential towards standardisation, namely, the CODECO flexible and modular architecture and semantic models: the CODECO OSS toolkits, use-cases, or the tools being developed to support experimentation in the project, such as CODEF, or CODAG.

The project is actively contributing to SDOs such as ESI (e.g., OSM, NFV), ISO (via EUCEI), IETF (e.g., GREEN, DetNet, CATS, BMWG), and IRTF (SUSTAIN, DINRG), addressing topics like secure connectivity, energy efficiency, Kubernetes benchmarking, and decentralised orchestration.

Beyond formal SDOs, CODECO actively collaborates with industry consortia and initiatives such as BDVA, EUCEI, AIOTI, and NetworkWorldEurope, contributing to white papers, reference architectures, taxonomies, and strategic agendas to ensure alignment with Europe's digital and AI transformation goals.

8 References

- [1] R. C. Sofia et al. (2024). CODECO Deliverable D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12819444>
- [2] L. I. Carvalho, R. C. Sofia, R. (2025). CARG: CODECO AI Resilience and Governance Toolkit - White Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15227994>
- [3] R. Sousa (Ed), John Soldatos (Ed), Dorine Matzakou (Ed), Xiaoming Fu (Use-case leader), Luis Contreras Murillo (Use-case leader), David Jimenez (Use-case leader), Jordi-Marias (Use-case leader), Rute C. Sofia (Ed./ (Use-case leader), & Andries Stam (Use-case leader). (2023). CODECO D8 - Fine-grained Use-case Design and Business Impact (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8143800>
- [4] E. Stephan, M. Palmero, B. Claise, L. M. Contreras. Requirements for Energy Efficient Management. IETF draft, Informational. Nov 2024 (active). Available: <https://www.ietf.org/archive/id/draft-stephan-green-ucs-and-reqs-01.txt>
- [5] A. Rodriguez-Natal, L. M. Contreras, M. Palmero, F. Munoz, J. Lindblad. Path Energy Traffic Ratio API (PETRA), IETF draft, informational, Oct. 2024 (active). Available: <https://www.ietf.org/archive/id/draft-petra-green-api-00.txt>
- [6] R. C. Sofia, P. Mendes, C. J. Bernardos, E. Schooler. Requirements for Reliable Wireless Industrial Services, IETF draft, Informational, July 2024 (expired). Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/draft-ietf-detnet-raw-industrial-req-01>
- [7] Y. Kehan, H. Shi, L. M. Contreras, J. Ros-Giralt. CATS metrics definition. IETF draft, informational, March 2025 (active). Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-cats-metric-definition/02/>
- [8] Y. Kehan, H. Shi, L. M. Contreras, H. Shi, S. Hang, Q. An. Computing-aware traffic steering (CATS) problem statement, use cases and requirements. IETF draft, informational, Feb 2025 (active). Available: <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-cats-usecases-requirements/06/>
- [9] S. Gusmeroli (Ed.), Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum: opportunities and challenges for the Manufacturing Industry, release 1.0 December 2024. AIOTI White paper, WG Standardisation, Available: <https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/CEI-Continuum-opportunities-and-challenges-for-Manufacturing-Final.pdf>
- [10] IoT and Edge Computing impact on Beyond 5G: enabling technologies and challenges, release 1.0. AIOTI White paper, WG Standardisation, November 2023. Available: <https://aioti.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/AIOTI-Report-IoT-and-Edge-impact-on-Beyond-5G-R3-Final.pdf>

